

ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL SUCCESS

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Abstract

Education being a lifelong process prepares an individual for a respectable future. In the entire teaching learning process, the teacher is the lighthouse that guides the students to learn certain concepts facts, and figures from the prescribed syllabus for examination purpose but also help them gain good marks and results. They also make them capable of influencing learning, principles, thoughts, values, attitudes & deeds of next generation. This is possible only from good and effective teachers. So, a teacher needs to have such essential skills, personality characteristics and behaviour which can help him in creating warm classroom climate, to promote enthusiasm, motivation and interactive teacher-student relationship. Emotional intelligence of a teacher plays a key role in his successful career. Professional success of an individual mainly depends upon the combination of the two vital components, intelligence and skills. Professionalism demands teachers to be innovative in their approaches, flexible in their attitudes and always upgrading themselves with the day to day development in their subject matter. All the same, they should be capable of recognizing the values of human potentials, understanding the different needs of students and provide appropriate enriched environment for their wholesome growth. When the teachers are well equipped decorated in moral, emotional, intellectual, practical and professional communication skills, only then the dream of a learned society can be realised. The present study is an attempt to explore the role of emotional intelligence competencies in the professional success story of a teacher.

Key words: - Emotional Intelligence, behaviour, professionalism, potential, competency, Success.

INTRODUCTION

Education being a lifelong process prepares an individual for a respectable future. In the entire teaching learning process, the

teacher is the lighthouse that guides the students the future nation builders. As such the development of any democratic country depends on the status and performances of teachers. High achievement of the students, better performance, and exposure in the area of growing competition are some of the issues lying at the hands of the teacher. The teacher is the ultimate agent who not only teaches the students to learn certain facts, concepts and figures from the syllabus for examination purpose and gain good marks or results but capable of influencing the principles, thoughts, values, attitudes and the deeds of the next generation. Only good and effective teachers can do so. Hence, the importance of a teacher in the educational process is unquestionable. It is rightly said by the **Education Commission** (1966) that “The future of India is now being shaped in the classrooms”. So, a teacher needs to have such essential skills, personality characteristics and behaviour which can help him in creating warm classroom climate, to promote enthusiasm, motivation and interactive teacher-student relationship. Emotional intelligence of a teacher plays a key role in this regard. Professional success of an individual mainly depends upon the combination of the two vital components, **intelligence and skills**. Professionalism demands teachers to have innovative approaches, flexible attitude and upgrading themselves with the day to day development in their subject matter. All the same they should be capable of recognizing the value of human potentials, understanding the different needs of the students and provide appropriate enriched environment for their wholesome growth. When the teachers are well equipped decorated with moral, emotional, intellectual, practical and professional communication skills, then only the dream of a learned society can be realised.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- Exploring the role of emotional intelligence competencies in teachers' professional success.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Interpretative study of the literature available on the subject of the

study has been used i.e. journals, books and electronic resources.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

With the dawn of the 21st century, the human mind explored the latent dimension which is now being held accountable for success more than intelligence. This dimension termed as Emotional Intelligence(EI) is measured as Emotional Quotient (EQ). The concept of EI is an evolving one and has found its origin in the cradle of a variety of disciplines. The popularity of the concept of 'Emotional Intelligence' has raised an enormous interest in the field of psychology, management and education. It has more scope and relevance in the field of education. However, the authenticity of such need was first brought into our notice vividly by Charles Darwin in 1870 through the publication of "The Expression of The Emotions in Man and Animal" in which he tried to highlight the role of emotional expression in our survival and adaptation but the term emotional intelligence was first introduced in 1990 by Dr. John Mayer and Dr. Peter Salovey in the journal 'Imagination, Cognition and Personality'. They defined emotional intelligence as "the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and use this information to guide one's thinking and actions". Later, this concept was propagated by Daniel Goleman. According to him "Emotional intelligence is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships". Bar-On claimed that "emotional intelligence is an array of non-cognitive capabilities, competencies and skills that influence one's ability to succeed in coping with the environmental demands and pressure". Thus, EI is an umbrella term that captures a broad collection of interpersonal skills and intrapersonal skills. Interpersonal skills concerns "outer self" whereas intrapersonal skills concerns an "inner self." Consequently, where the skills and abilities comprising one's intra-personal skills help one in knowing and managing one's

own feeling and emotions in a proper way, the skills and abilities belonging to inter-personal skills of EI, on the other hand, prove helpful in interacting and getting along with others by taking care of their feelings and emotions.

If a person just follows 'mind', then he is nothing but 'machine', if a person just follows 'heart', then he is just 'tender' (child), if a person is able to combine both, then he is emotionally intelligent, which means he is mentally as well as emotionally strong. It has been experimentally proven that emotions do matter and the possession of skills and abilities regarding knowing and managing the emotions helps one in a great way to achieve success in all walks of his life. Likewise, one's feelings and emotions are no longer treated as working against one's intelligent functioning but rather taken as a quite helpful source and powerhouse for igniting and putting one into action by becoming "street smart" for realization of the self-defined goals. Thus apart from the traditional general intelligence it is one's content of EI that pushes him wonderfully towards the unmatched success in life by helping him suitable in knowing and managing the emotions of the self and others in proper way. Thus, the power of EQ has now begun to be realized in each corner and every aspect of our lives. Therefore, EI is now taken as the golden key and gateway for the attainment of what we say as success in our personal, social and professional lives.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE COMPETENCIES

Emotional Intelligence is a broad concept comprising many different competencies. Emotional competencies cluster into groups, each based on common underlying emotional intelligence capacity. These underlying emotional competencies are very much important if teachers are to successfully learn the competencies necessary to professionally succeed at the schools and colleges.

Daniel Goleman's mixed model of emotional intelligence tells that one's EI consists of relevant personality traits as well as number of functioning abilities or skills. **Goleman** defines an emotional competency as "a learned capacity based on emotional intelligence

that results in outstanding performance at work". Any one's emotional intelligence is what determines his/her potential for learning the practical skills that are based on its emotional intelligence cluster. A person's emotional competence shows how much of that potential has been transferred into the job capabilities. Simply being high in emotional intelligence doesn't guarantee that a person will have learned the emotional competencies. It means only that they have excellent potential to learn them.

Daniel Goleman sets out a framework of emotional intelligence that reflects how an individual's potential for mastering the skills of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management translates into a job success. This model is a modification of the model he used in 1998. In the current model there are twenty competencies which are divided into four clusters of general EI abilities. The framework of EI competencies is as shown in the figure below:

Figure-1

THE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE COMPETENCIES FRAMEWORK

	Self Personal Competence	Other Social Competence
RECOGNITION	<p><u>Self-Awareness</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional Awareness • Accurate Assessment • Self-Confidence 	<p><u>Social Awareness</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy • Service Orientation • Organizational Awareness
REGULATION	<p><u>Self-Management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-Control • Trustworthiness • Conscientiousness • Adaptability • Achievement Drive • Initiative 	<p><u>Relationship Management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing Others • Influence • Communication • Conflict Management • Leadership • Change Catalyst • Building Bonds • Teamwork & Collaboration

Source: raniakort.com

- i. **Self -Awareness:** - The ability to read one's emotions and recognize their impact while using gut feelings to guide decisions.

- ii. Self - Management:** - Involves the ability for controlling one's emotions and impulses and adapting to changing circumstances.
- iii. Social Awareness:** - The ability to serve, understand and react to others emotions while comprehending social networks.
- iv. Relationship Management:** - The ability to inspire, influence and develop others while managing conflict.

ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL SUCCESS

Teachers today are not only educators but therapists, parent's substitutes, mentors and many more. In order to perform these roles teachers need to have well balanced personality traits for their success in this profession. They must rise above the crowd and make a lasting impression on his students and institutions. However, to be an effective teacher doesn't solely depend on teacher's intellectual quotient (IQ) but it also depends upon how well he or she can use emotional intelligence competencies in their professional capacities.

Teachers with high self-awareness competence are fully aware of their emotions, feelings that facilitate them to teach, interact with students and bear the potential to assess themselves properly. As they know their strengths and weaknesses thoroughly, they can be good guides, mentors and counsellors for the students in the institutions. Such teachers can visualize the pros and cons of any situation and are able to initiate change with courage and confidence. They also take efforts to learn new things and keep themselves up-to-date. Teachers with high self-awareness are able to monitor their actions and act accordingly along the correct path if required. They are dynamic and emotionally well equipped personality.

Being aware of emotional feelings and its impact is not sufficient enough to become successful. Teacher should try to regulate the feelings and the consequent reactions as per the situational requirements. Teachers with high self-regulation competence can

regulate themselves very efficiently and remain the source of inspiration to every student. These teachers show integrity and honesty in their approach. They are reliable, authentic and accountable. They can easily build rapport with students. They are innovative, effective and open to new information. They are deeply committed to the profession. They can handle any challenging environment in the institution. Teachers with high EI can easily maintain their emotional balance and improve the emotional well being of their students.

Teachers with high social awareness competence can easily grasp the problems, worries and difficulties of students very quickly. Such capacity facilitates them to act according to the level and the need of the students. They are able to develop nurturing relationships with students which reduce misconduct in the classroom.

Teachers with high relationship management competence are multi-talented. They can positively influence students, manage any difficulty or conflict in the day to day functioning of institution. They show tremendous maturity and growth in their way of communicating a message or teaching in a class. Thus teachers with high EI can broaden the skyline of the students.

Therefore we can say that teachers who possess these competencies have emotionally stable personality. Each of these competencies is directly or indirectly related to the teaching and learning atmosphere. Teachers who own these competencies are able to make the experience of teaching and learning more memorable, enjoyable and intellectually stimulating both for themselves and for the students.

Other than that as a teacher, they play a significant role as an employee. They perform multiple tasks such as, organization's decision making, leadership, strategic and technical breakthrough, open and honest communication, trusting relations and teamwork, custom, loyalty and creativity as well as innovation. Thus, teachers with high EI are an asset for any institutions. **Swati Patra (2004)**

rightly opines that in the changing competitive environment one need more than just brains to achieve organizational development. EI can help in creating an enthusiastic work environment and efficient administration.

IMPORTANCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHER EDUCATION CURRICULUM

Teaching is a challenging profession and the levels of emotional intelligence possessed by teachers have a considerable impact on the quality of education and the quality of students produced. A teacher who is quite sympathetic to the feelings and welfare of his students, his non-egoistic attitude and helpful nature, straight-forwardness, love of wisdom, truth and goodness and eagerness of understanding and guiding his students to their goals may be a subject of admiration and respect from his students, their parents and the segment of the society to which he belongs. So, the concept of EI should be included in the syllabus and the curriculum should be designed in accordance with the teacher training programme. Lessons related to EI competencies should given importance in the classroom activities. It will help in stabilizing the teacher's EI.

Emotional intelligence is the capability to express, manage and control emotions of self and others. Teaching is a natural and emotional practice which involves emotional understanding, emotional relationship and emotional labour. Teachers need to value emotional bonds with students and educate them as emotional and social beings. It requires high level of emotional intelligence. As such, it becomes necessary to develop and maintain EI competencies of student teachers, during pre-service teacher education training. The purpose being that they may work with their students in a more effective manner and also may serve as important facilitators as well as role models for inculcating emotional competencies in them. The empowerment energy and enlightenment received through emotional intelligence plays wonder in one's life. Therefore, our future teachers should be trained by providing rich and varied experience to develop their EI during their training programme.

CONCLUSION

By knowing the role of emotional intelligence in a teacher's professional success it becomes extremely important to develop and sustain emotional intelligence competencies in themselves. This helps them to develop the same quality among their students. As it is known fact the present generation of students is more emotionally troubled than the previous. Most of them are growing more lonely and depressed, more angry and unruly, more nervous and prone to worry, more impulsive and aggressive. So, there is a magnanimous role of the teacher to control and balance the emotional health of the students. People with well-developed emotional skills are effective in their lives, mastering the habits of the mind and faster in their productivities.

Emotional intelligence is not an inherited phenomenon. The skills associated with it can be learned and developed at any stage, age and juncture of one's life for making their use in getting success in life. The successful development of emotional skills needs motivation, effort, time, support, and sustained practice. It is also suggested that teachers should attend some orientation, workshops and training sessions to learn techniques to improve EI in their services. The teachers should also develop an appreciation of fine arts; music, poetry and literature that would help them sublime their own emotions as well as those of their students. Teachers should also have a spiritual faith that makes us follow the right path in times of turmoil, teaching every human on earth tolerance and stability of emotions. So, this study will be useful to teachers, teacher educators and also educational administrators to sharpen and execute their emotional intelligence skills in their professional life.

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